

Yield and quality characteristics of improved basmati donors. Hyderabad, India, 1988.

Character	Pusa 367-152 (Pusa 167-2/Type 3)	Pusa 615-140-10-10 (IET10364) (Pusa 167/Karnal Local)	Pusa 751-1-2 (Pusa 367-4-2-2/Type 3)	Traditional local varieties		
				Karnal Local	Basmati 370	Type 3
Plant height (cm)	80-85	90-95	90-100	135-150	135-150	135-150
Growth duration (d)	145-150	135-140	140-145	145-150	135-140	135-140
Yield (t/ha)	3.0-4.0	4.0-5.0	2.5-3.0	2.0-2.5	2.0-3.0	2.0-3.0
Test grain weight (g)	25.92	22.80	27.54	22.00	20.53	18.60
Length of milled rice (mm)	7.63	6.98	8.37	7.35	6.87	6.71
Breadth of milled rice (mm)	2.00	1.70	1.90	1.78	1.89	1.84
L:B ratio	3.81	4.11	4.40	4.13	3.63	3.64
Length of kernel after cooking (mm)	16.20	14.70	18.37	13.89	13.64	13.22
Elongation ratio	2.12	2.01	2.19	1.89	1.98	1.97
Alkali spreading value	4	4	4	4	4	4
Amylose (%)	24.00	28.00	24.50	25.50	22.00	22.50
Presence of aroma ^a	M.S.	S	S.S.	S	S	S

^a M.S. = mildly scented, S = scented, S.S. = strongly scented.

and low grain number. In spite of poor yield, their unique cooking quality fetches the highest premium in the national and international markets.

Karnal Local, Basmati 370, and Type 3 are the most widely cultivated varieties. However, Karnal Local's higher kernel length and higher length:breadth ratio give it preference in the market.

After two decades of intensive

convergent breeding with rigorous screening and selection, IARI has developed three promising basmati lines: Pusa 367-152, Pusa 615-140-10-1, and Pusa 751-1-2 (see table). Pusa 367-152 has excellent plant type with stiff stem and dark green erect leaves. It has desirable cooking qualities; however, grain shattering, late maturity, and mild aroma are drawbacks. Pusa 615-140-10-1 has good plant type and all important

basmati components, but with relatively higher amylose content. Pusa 751-1-2 is much superior to traditional basmati in cooking quality and aroma but does not yield well because of low grain number and relatively moderate tillering.

Among them, Pusa 615-140-10-1 (IET10364) has been selected for farm trials. All three lines may be useful as donors in the basmati rice improvement program. □

Saleem and Satya released for Andhra Pradesh, India

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Saleem and Satya were released for general cultivation in 1987 for Andhra Pradesh, particularly for Telangana region. Semidwarf Saleem, derived from GEB 24/Sigadis//IR8/RNR8102, has 135 d duration in monsoon. It will grow in winter with irrigation. From 1972 to 1982, it yielded 6.4 t/ha average in monsoon, 27% more than Jaya, Jagannath, and Prakash. In winter, it registered 7.5 t/ha, 10.8% more than Jaya and Sona. In farmers' fields over 7 districts, it outyielded Tella Hamsa and Mahsuri by 21%. It has long slender grains with length:breadth ratio 3.5.

Satya, from the cross Tella Hamsa/Rasi, has 120 d duration in monsoon and 130 d in winter and

tolerates cold in vegetative phase. It tolerates bacterial blight and sheath blight. It has white long slender grains. From 1980 to 1986, it produced 5.4 t/ha

in monsoon and 5.0 t/ha in winter, 14.3% more than Tella Hamsa in monsoon and 38.4% more than Tella Hamsa and IR50 in winter. □

Mutant glutinous rice variety Xiang-zao-nou 1

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Xiang-zao-nou 1 is a new glutinous rice variety with good quality, high yields, and multiple resistance. It was developed by irradiating F₂ dry seeds of IR29/ Wen-Xwan-qing with 27.9 kR of ⁶⁰Co-gamma rays.

Xiang-zao-nou 1 has good plant type, desirable yielding components, and wide adaptability. It matures in 117 d in the early season in Hunan Province, China. Generally, it can yield 6.75 t/ha in the

early season or 6 t/ha in late season. It is highly resistant to bacterial blight and blast, and is very good in grain quality and glutinosity. This variety was grown on more than 220,000 ha 1983-87. □

P.837 — a promising new rice variety for Pondicherry, India

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In Pondicherry region (11°45' - 12°15' N and 79°35' - 80°00' E), half the crop area is planted to rice Aug-Sep to Dec-

Jan (samba season). Samba rice is always less productive because of cold weather coupled with pests and diseases. A medium to fine rice grain type is preferred by farmers.

Breeding line P.837, a derivative of the cross IR8/H.4, appears promising for this area. It matures in 145-150 d. Grains are medium slender and translucent. Yields average 5.8 t/ha, an increase of 29, 22, and 23% over IR20, Co 43, and Mahsuri puthae (white ponni), respectively.

P.837 has recorded resistance to such major pests as brown planthopper and leaffolder. It was tolerant of the major diseases blast and helminthosporium (see table). □

Field reaction^a of P.837 to major insects and diseases, compared to check varieties. Pondicherry, India, 1984-87.

Variety	Insects			Diseases		
	BPH	Leaffolder	Stem borer (%)	Blast	Helminthosporium	Sheath rot
				<i>1984-85</i>		
P.837	3	3	8.5	1	3	3
IR20	9	3	14.0	1	7	5
				<i>1985-86</i>		
P.837	3	3	9.0	3	3	1
IR20	7	5	18.5	5	7	3
Co 43	5	7	16.0	5	5	7
				<i>1986-87</i>		
P.837	—	—	10.2	—	3	5
IR20	—	5	16.0	—	7	7
Co 43	—	7	16.5	—	3	7
Co 1009	—	5	14.5	—	5	5

^aStandard evaluation system for rice.

Gall midge (GM)-resistant rice cultivars

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So far three varieties resistant to GM—Kakatiya, Surekha, and Pothana—have been released for general cultivation. Cultivars suited to different cropping practices and with improved grain type also are needed.

One local practice is sowing rice under dry conditions and converting to irrigation when water is available in tanks. Two short-duration, GM-resistant varieties—WGL 18011(CR44/W.12708) and WGL 20471-97 (BC.5/W.12708)—were sown in the 1987 wet season (WS) using the local seed drill at 30-cm spacing in 73.2 m² plot. This dry condition was converted to wet conditions at 40 d.

Both varieties matured in 100 d and yielded 3.0 t/ha. They have long slender grains. In minikit tests in the dry season (DS), WGL 20471-97 averaged 6.3 t yield/ha, 47% higher than Tella Hamsa. Both varieties are suitable for late, direct sowing.

Two GM-resistant cultures—WGL 44645 and WGL 48684—have superior grain quality. WGL 44645 (WGL 23022/Surekha) has a 125 d duration in

WS and 135 d in DS. It has stiff straw and long slender grains. Grain quality is superior to that of varieties released earlier. In minikit trials, it yielded 4.2 t/ha against 2.8 t/ha for Tella Hamsa. It is tolerant of stem borer and hispa.

WGL 48684 (WGL 27120/(Mashuri/WGL 17672)/Surekha) has a 135 d duration in WS. Grains are medium slender. It is also suitable for DS provided sowing is before December.

Both varieties have 9% protein content. □

TR-RNR-21, a new medium-duration rice variety, released in Andhra Pradesh (A.P.)

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TR-RNR-21 is a derivative of the cross IR8/TR-5. TR-5 is a N_f-induced dwarf mutant of salinity-resistant SR-26-B.

In initial yield evaluations in 1972-78, it gave 54% higher yields than Jaya in the wet season and 19% in the dry

season and compared favorably with IR8 and Sona.

Compared with Pankaj, Jaya, RP-4-14, Sona, Surekha, RNR-32341, and Prabhat, in 1975-80 trials, TR-RNR-21 gave average yields 10.1% higher than those of the highest yielding checks and 19.8% higher than the average of 7 checks (see table). In minikit trials at more than 90 sites in 9 districts of Telangana region, mean grain yield (3.8 t/ha) was 19% higher than yield of local checks. TR-RNR-21 was released in 1987 as Hari, for general cultivation

Relative yield performance of TR-RNR-21 (Hari) at Andhra Pradesh Agriculture University and in the All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project, Rajendranagar, Hyderabad, India.

Variety	Mean yield (t/ha)		
	Monsoon season (5 trials)	Dry season (6 trials)	Total
TR-RNR-21 (<i>Hari</i>)	5.4	6.3	5.9
Highest yielding check	4.9	5.8	5.4
All checks combined	4.7	5.1	4.9